

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B491		
Date:	30 NOV 2009		
Take Off:	14:59:01Z	Z	Z
Landing:	18:42:52Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	3h 53m 51s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: THAW

Operating Area: Aberystwyth

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM	Robbie Voaden	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Geraint Vaughan	Aberystwyth
5	Flight manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry / AVAPS training	Axel Wellpot	FAAM
9	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office
10			
11			
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 1800 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
Y	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
Y	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
Y	ViRC chat log
Y	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-12-11	Mo Smith	Initial version
R1			
r2			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B491

Date: 30 November 2009

Project: THAW

Location: Aberystwyth

Start End

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
130631		Start-Up	0.40 kft	307	52'12.56N, 0'10.45E
145333		ASP	0.35 kft	137	Open
145901		T/O	4.9 kft	301	Cambridge
150626		Video	10.0 kft	284	Start all 4
153746	160518	Profile 1	28.0 - 16.0 kft	304	Spiral over Aber
160903	161313	Profile 1	15.9 - 14.1 kft	222	Pause for pilot's instrumnts
160928		Video	15.8 kft	181	Restart after software crash
161321	161945	Profile 2	14.1 - 24.0 kft	342	
161946	162407	Run 1	24.0 - 24.1 kft	152	Porpoise
162527	163505	Run 2	24.3 - 24.2 kft	336	Porpoise
163025		Event	24.3 kft	329	Ovhd Aber
164124	164714	Run 3.1	24.3 - 24.2 kft	041	Porpoise
164216		JW & Nevz	24.3 kft	025	Zero cal
164324		Event	24.3 kft	007	Ovhd Aber
165227		Sonde	28.0 kft	258	Launch #01
170446	174454	Profile 3	28.0 - 10.0 kft	269	Spiral
170619		Video	27.2 kft	078	Stop UFC (dark)
174609	180043	Profile 4	10.1 - 25.0 kft	011	
184252		Land	0.22 kft	050	Cambridge
184535		ASP	0.23 kft	353	Closed
184929		Shutdown	0.24 kft	051	52'12.55N, 0'10.45E

Mission Scientist's Log 2

Flight No B...491 Date 30/11/09 Name Peter Brown Page 1 of 2

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
150208					T/O Cambridge.
153746	P1	28000		52 24 3 54	poss wavelike motions
—					in W, just bit start.
—					Satcom lost at 1540.
1544		25300			no contrast, now or at start.
1553		21000			W offset ~ 2ms ⁻¹ in turn. on Horace display
—		21000			O ₃ 40 - back down to
—					troposph. values +
		20000			another layer of higher O ₃
—					~ 55 ppb
161327	P1/P2	14000			end/start.
161946	R1	24000			wind 39/350
162345	-				end.
162527	R2	24300	316		into wind purpose. 42/343
163205	"				end.
164124	R3.1	24300	024		
1647			058		41/348
164714	3.1				end. climbing for sonde.
1652	-	28000			sonde .1 close overhead After.
170446	P3	"			start.
		23500			O ₃ peak 78
		22300			O ₃ min 50
—		21500			O ₃ peak 82 e strong
—					O gradient

Sortie Brief: BAe146 Flight B491 – 30 November 2009

Geraint Vaughan and Phil Brown

Mission Scientist 1: Phil Brown

Mission Scientists: Geraint Vaughan

Location: Over MST radar site, Capel Dewi, Aberystwyth, 52°25'28" N, 4° 0'18.89" W

Aims: Flight in the tropopause region to address two scientific problems. The first is to better understand the mechanisms that produce MST radar echoes in a non-turbulent atmosphere.

The second is the measurement of upper tropospheric humidity with the Buck hygrometer, across the tropopause and in cirrus clouds

The major part of the flight will be spent performing profiles around the MST radar site. The plan is to execute slow descents (500 ft/min or 150 m s⁻¹) as a combination of 540° descending turns and a constant altitude racetrack along-wind to allow the aircraft to regain its position:

The descending 3π radian section is 18.85 nm (35.9 km) long and the racetrack 26.2 nm (48.5 km), making a total of 45 nm (83 km). At a ground speed of 300 kt this pattern will take 9 minutes to execute, 3.8 of which will be spent descending. Therefore each manoeuvre will descend around 1900 ft or 575 m.

Item	Time (UTC)	Manoeuvre	Distance (km)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	1500	Take off Cambridge, ascend to 28000 ft and head for Aberystwyth. On transit, look for patches of cirrus. We want to fly around the edges of cirrus clouds and just into them.	230 as the crow flies	45	45
2	1545	Arrive Aberystwyth. Perform spiral descent from 28000 ft to 15000 ft (heights as advised, based on ozone measurements)		50	95
3	1635	ascend to level chosen by aircraft scientist		5	100
4	1640	Fly porpoising legs away and towards radar along-wind, 100 ft amplitude for 30 km (16 miles).		8	108
5	1648	Repeat 4 and 5 across-wind		13	121
6	1700	Ascend to level to be advised and launch dropsonde		5	126
7	1755	Descend to 10000' (or as advised by a/c scientist) using above pattern to 15000' then descending along racetrack as well		55	181
8	1800	Return to Cambridge	230	45	
9	1845	Land in Cambridge.			

asxx 30/11/2009 18:00 UTC

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 30/11/09

Flight No: B 491

Pre-Flighter: SLOWAN

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24				
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<u>External Checks</u>				
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44		Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
		ICEX applied		
		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more	
		Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B491
Date: 30 Nov 09

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC zeros okay but signal output always flatlines (at 0uA on control unit meter). DLU reading always 6346 DRSU.
2. Detachment Toolkit – lock fallen out, down back of drawers
3. MPDS – lost after start of spiral profile, recovered okay when level
4. Video recording software, crashed at 1609, restarted then okay.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS – downloaded 3 x radiosonde plots – 101kB

Satcom H – One call out and two in, all FAAM test – all worked fine

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

B491 12:56:06–18:50:08

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

vIRC record – flight B491

*** FAAMOpsCranfiel (FAAMOpsBas@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
<james> Hi FAAM_flt_man. Are you the right person to ask about getting a seat on tomorrow morning's flight?
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] No - I am.
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Drop me an EMail to guat@faam.ac.uk
<james> Thanks Guy. Will do. Looks like it could be an interesting one for the TDL, so I might as well fly since we'll be in Cambridge.
<Dan_Housley> Flight peeps today, most of whom seem to have dissapeared, ... the Sonde data has been emailed to the Aircraft
<Dan_Housley> have they just taken off? is comms cut during take off? i'm completly ignorant of these things
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Aircraft - could you confirm that you're seeing messages from vIRC please.
*** FAAM_flt_man (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Hello aircraft - can anybody see these messages from on board?
<FAAM_MS3> Hi from the aircraft. Last message received ok.
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Thanks Mission Science
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Can see your position reports fine, satcom messages looking suspect
<FAAM_MS3> Hi Dan. email and 3 attachments received OK.
<Dan_Housley> rgr
<Dan_Housley> good stuff
<Dan_Housley> the sondes heading to Caerdydd... should be out of your way
<Dan_Housley> and just to let you know but the winds have picked up here @ 8-9 km it's 40-45 m/s
<Dan_Housley> presumably you'll be flying lower than that today?
<FAAM_MS3> We plan to start at 28000ft - about 8.4km by mental arithmetic - and working downwards.
<Dan_Housley> so rough at the top then for you
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] James Dorsey now added to the crew list for B492 tomorrow morning.
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Read error: Connection reset by peer]
*** james (james@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Quit: Konversation terminated!]
*** JimCR_FAAM (JimCrawfor@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
<Dan_Housley> how's the flight?
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Read error: Connection reset by peer]
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
<FAAM_MS3> Hi Dan we lose internetr during spiral turns.
<Dan_Housley> yeah i figured
<Dan_Housley> how's it going?
<FAAM_MS3> climbing to 24000ft for porpoise runs. this is just at base of high ozone layer.
<FAAM_MS3> do you have cloud over the site right now?
<Dan_Housley> yup about 6/8ths

<Dan_Housley> patchy
<FAAM_MS3> so probably not good for the lidar then?
<Dan_Housley> the satellite earlier seemed to suggest that it will be clear, but we'll see how it goes
<Dan_Housley> i'm going to keep it on, so long as no precip
<Dan_Housley> civil twilight is in around 30-40 minutes
<Dan_Housley> we'll make a judgement then whether to turn it on or not
<FAAM_MS3> rgr.
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Read error: Connection reset by peer]
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Civil sunset for Cardiff is at 1641 today, legal night starts 30 minutes later.
<Dan_Housley> rgr, water vapour lidar is running now
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
<FAAM_MS3> Now on another porpoise run at 24300ft
<FAAM_MS3> just passed overhead
<FAAM_MS3> now climbing again for dropsonde eject
<FAAM_MS3> sonde launched at 1652
<FAAM_MS3> starting another spiral descent at 28000ft
<Hugo> understood. skies have started to clear. so we should be able to see you
<Hugo> we can see you :-)
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 600 seconds]
*** FAAM_MS3 (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146
<FAAM_MS3> Hi all. We've finished spirals now. Just doing one more profile ascent to 25000ft and then going home.
<Dan_Housley> heh ok, caught the 146 in the radar a few times
<Dan_Housley> getting ready to launch a sonde as soon as you depart
<Hugo> that makes sense. we've been following your spiraliness.
<Hugo> we're waving :-)
<FAAM_MS3> OK we just finished ascent. Heading back to Cambridge.
<Dan_Housley> we can see
<Dan_Housley> we're launching a sonde to chase you back
<FAAM_MS3> Is the lidar working?
<Hugo> All lidars are go.
<Hugo> Thanks for coming.
<FAAM_MS3> Excellent. Good humidity measurements up here.
<FAAM_MS3> For FAAMOps ETA 1840
<FAAM_MS3> Thanks to all on the ground - think its been a good day.
<Hugo> Thanks you sky people - clearing up nicely now.
<Dan_Housley> We'll put the kettle on, get the bourbons out
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Thanks Mission Science, I'll probably be heading home about 1841
*** Hugo (Hugo@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146

<Dan_Housley> for peeps in the sky it's 0.9 C on the ground

<Dan_Housley> put your gloves on ;)

<Dan_Housley> toodles! o/

*** Dan_Housley (djhousley@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146

Flight Map – flight B491

Position Reports from G-Luxe flight B491

[Map](#)

Date/Time	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude
30/11/09 1458Z	52°12.1N	0°10.1E	226 ft
30/11/09 1502Z	52°19.1N	0°14.6E	5147 ft
30/11/09 1508Z	52°22.7N	0°25.6W	9688 ft
30/11/09 1515Z	52°8.2N	1°15.6W	9738 ft
30/11/09 1523Z	52°4.4N	2°9.4W	16854 ft
30/11/09 1529Z	52°8.4N	2°59.9W	24833 ft
30/11/09 1532Z	52°16.5N	3°21.6W	27212 ft
30/11/09 1537Z	52°25.7N	3°49.5W	27268 ft
30/11/09 1544Z	52°21.6N	3°54.9W	24371 ft
30/11/09 1547Z	52°22.1N	3°55.6W	23219 ft
30/11/09 1555Z	52°21.7N	3°56.7W	19958 ft
30/11/09 1600Z	52°22.2N	3°58.2W	17681 ft
30/11/09 1605Z	52°31.2N	4°2.1W	15588 ft
30/11/09 1610Z	52°23.9N	4°2.6W	15269 ft
30/11/09 1619Z	52°30.8N	4°19.5W	22917 ft
30/11/09 1624Z	52°3.9N	3°48.5W	23642 ft
30/11/09 1627Z	52°15.7N	3°53.1W	23764 ft
30/11/09 1631Z	52°29.6N	4°2.7W	23744 ft
30/11/09 1635Z	52°42.4N	4°7.1W	23596 ft
30/11/09 1641Z	52°18N	4°10.3W	23724 ft
30/11/09 1645Z	52°28N	3°48.8W	23580 ft
30/11/09 1655Z	52°12.7N	4°1W	27337 ft
30/11/09 1700Z	52°27.5N	3°43.7W	27307 ft
30/11/09 1705Z	52°24.2N	4°4.4W	26585 ft
30/11/09 1710Z	52°22.2N	3°57.8W	24810 ft

30/11/09 1715Z	52°27.5N	3°57.7W	22688 ft
30/11/09 1723Z	52°24N	4°4.2W	19046 ft
30/11/09 1730Z	52°24N	4°4.4W	16355 ft
30/11/09 1735Z	52°23.5N	3°56.2W	14531 ft
30/11/09 1741Z	52°23.7N	3°58.1W	11165 ft
30/11/09 1745Z	52°23N	4°0.9W	9787 ft
30/11/09 1750Z	52°23.4N	3°56W	14367 ft
30/11/09 1755Z	52°22.1N	3°55.5W	18550 ft
30/11/09 1800Z	52°19.2N	4°4.6W	23820 ft
30/11/09 1805Z	52°11.1N	3°18.8W	24407 ft
30/11/09 1810Z	52°3.7N	2°30.4W	22848 ft
30/11/09 1815Z	51°58.9N	1°54.2W	9518 ft
30/11/09 1820Z	52°1.8N	1°24.4W	4937 ft
30/11/09 1825Z	52°7.3N	0°55.9W	4924 ft
30/11/09 1830Z	52°16N	0°29.8W	4888 ft
30/11/09 1835Z	52°21.2N	0°0.9W	2424 ft

Last changed 30 November 2009, 18:36Z

Use browser REFRESH function to obtain the latest version

Position is reported only at intervals of several minutes and may not accurately reflect the aircraft track.

Recent messages to/from G-LUXE

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 13:04

G
From: Test B491 301109 30/11/09 1302Z
To: Flight Manager

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 13:04

From: Test B491 301109 30/11/09 1302Z
To: Flight Manager

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 14:55

Mo,
James Dorsey would like to join the flight tomorrow. He may catch you on x-chat, but if not can you let me know if it's poss, and I'll respond to him?
Also, please let Jamie know his car will be collected from his home address now, after the 1st flight tomorrow.
Any problems, let me know.
Alison

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 15:06

Q aepe@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1503Z
To: Alison

Thanks Alison.
Will try the chat now.
chrs
M

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 15:19

Hello aircraft.

Can you confirm whether you've received this.

Assuming currently that you can't see vIRC.

Have a good flight.

Guy

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 15:27

Q guat@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1524Z
To: Guy

Hi Guy,
Yes virc is working on a/c. Phil B has control of it and has just uploaded the upsonde plots. Satcom c all okay so far too.

chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:03

last posn rcd 1544
EGSC 301520Z 33009KT 270V020 9999 FEW018 SCT033 06/03 Q1002

EGSC 301405Z 3015/3021 33011KT 9999 SCT035
PROB30
TEMPO 3015/3017 35015G25KT
EGNX 301550Z 32011KT 9999 FEW035 SCT045 05/01 Q1006

EGNX 301059Z 3012/0112 34014KT 9999 SCT025
PROB30
TEMPO 3012/3017 35018G32KT
BECMG 3021/3024 VRB04KT
PROB30 0103/0109 4000 BR
BECMG 0109/0112 17010KT
EGGW 301550Z 34014KT 9999 SCT029 05/02 Q1003

EGGW 301103Z 3012/0112 01015KT 9999 SCT030
PROB40
TEMPO 3012/3018 01018G30KT
PROB30
TEMPO 3012/3014 9000 -SHRA
BECMG 0101/0104 34005KT
PROB40 0101/0110 2000 BR
EGSS 301550Z 33011KT 9999 -SHRA FEW014 BKN026 05/03 Q1002

R:\Data\Flt Mgr Data_Logs\B482-Bnnn NovDec2009\B491\B491 Flight Following.doc

EGSS 301103Z 3012/0118 36014KT 9999 SCT015
PROB40
TEMPO 3012/3018 36018G30KT
PROB30
TEMPO 3012/3014 9000 -SHRA BKN014
BECMG 0101/0104 34005KT
PROB40 0101/0110 3000 BR
BECMG 0115/0118 18010KT
sent 1600 pc

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:24

Mo, Have you spoken to James Dorsey? Do I need to?
Alison

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:49

Q aepe@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1644Z
To: Alison
Hi,
No I haven't but I believe Guy has. It would be
useful to get an update of any changes to the crew
list and timings (if there have been any since this morning).
chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:54

For Mo

No changes to timings for tomorrow.

James Dorsey added to first flight.

All else remains the same so far.

G?

1655 Monday 31 November.

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:59

last posn rcd 1645
EGSC 301620Z 33013G24KT 260V030 9999 FEW036 SCT049 06/02 Q1003

EGSC 301405Z 3015/3021 33011KT 9999 SCT035
PROB30
TEMPO 3015/3017 35015G25KT
EGGW 301650Z 34014KT 9999 -SHRA BKN041 05/02 Q1004

EGGW 301103Z 3012/0112 01015KT 9999 SCT030
PROB40
TEMPO 3012/3018 01018G30KT
PROB30
TEMPO 3012/3014 9000 -SHRA
BECMG 0101/0104 34005KT
PROB40 0101/0110 2000 BR
EGNX 301650Z 32009KT 9999 FEW025 04/00 Q1007

EGNX 301059Z 3012/0112 34014KT 9999 SCT025
PROB30
TEMPO 3012/3017 35018G32KT
BECMG 3021/3024 VRB04KT
PROB30 0103/0109 4000 BR
BECMG 0109/0112 17010KT
sent 1700 pc

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 17:31

Q guat@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1725Z
To: Guy

Thks Guy. V good flight so far. O3 up to 140ppb and dare
I say Buck workingdown to -70C.
chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 17:47

latest posn rcd 1735
EGSC 301720Z 32011KT 260V030 9999 FEW036 SCT049 05/03 Q1004

EGSC 301703Z 3018/3021 32009KT 9999 FEW040
EGGW 301720Z 35014KT 9999 FEW030 SCT044 04/02 Q1005

EGGW 301702Z 3018/0118 34009KT 9999 SCT035
PROB30 0101/0110 2000 BR
BECMG 0115/0118 18010KT
EGNX 301720Z 33010KT 9999 FEW025 04/01 Q1007

EGNX 301658Z 3018/0118 33010KT 9999 FEW025
BECMG 3021/3024 VRB04KT
PROB30 0103/0109 4000 BR
BECMG 0110/0113 16010KT

sent 1745 pc

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 18:01

S
UZUK80 EGRR 301752
XXAA 8017/ 99524 70040 18124 99002 05050 ///// 88999 77999
31313 09608 81652
51515 10190 00553
61616 FAAM THAW B491 OB 01
62626 SPL 5234N00398W 1702 AEV 20504 =
XXBB 80178 99524 70040 18124 00002 05050 11001 44359
21212 00002 ///// 11001 34597
31313 09608 81652
51515 10190 00553
61616 FAAM THAW B491 OB 01
62626 SPL 5234N00398W 1702 AEV 20504 =

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 18:08

Q peter.chappell@directflight.co.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1806Z
To: Peter
ETA 1840

Last changed 30 November 2009, 18:08Z

Choose A Flight Number To Show Instrument Status For It

Choose Flight

[back](#)

Key :

	Not Operated		
	Minor Problems		
	Ok		

B491

Primary Systems	Temperature	Remote Sensing	Cloud Physics	Aerosol	Chemistry
AMTG					
AVAPS					
Cabin Pressure Rmount					
Camera - Downward Facing					
Camera - Forward Facing	Hygrometry	BBR (red) Lower			
Camera - Rearward Facing					
Camera - Upward Facing					
Cruciform GPS					
DLU AERACK					
DLU BBR Lower					
DLU BBR Upper					
DLU Core Chem					
DLU Core Consoles					
DLU Port Aft					
DLU Port Fwd					
DLU Stbd Fwd					
Fax machine					
GIN Applanix POSAV510					
HORACE					
INU Honeywell H423					
Printer					
Radar Altimeter					
RVSM IAS					
RVSM Static Pressure					
S9 Static Press Rmount					
Satcom Phones					
Satcom Data					
Turb Diff Centre-Static					
Turb Diff Left-Right					
Turb Diff Up-Down					
Turb Horizontal Check					
Turb Vertical Check					
Weather Radar					
XR5 GPS					

Flight B491 16:54:39

Heading 148 deg Speed 315 knots Height 28.0kft Press 328mb

Lat 52°12.0'N Long 4°6.0'W Wind 51 ms-1/ 348 deg

Temp -44.72C Dewpoint -52.5C

From 16:17:34 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT

++++ OZONE MIXING RATIO

28.07

55.51

Kft

ppb

● All

○

Flight B491 16:48:05

Heading 353 deg Speed 298 knots Height 25.2kft Press 371mb

Lat 52°30.0'N Long 3°24.0'W Wind 46 ms-1/ 344 deg

Temp -39.51C Dewpoint -59.07C

From 15:13:54 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT
OZONE MIXING RATIO

60483

64.34

secs

ppb

All sc

Flight B491 16:01:33

Heading 280 deg Speed 300 knots Height 17.2kft Press 522mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 3°54.0'W Wind 11 ms-1/ 323 deg

Temp -27.83C Dewpoint -47.85C

From 15:13:54 to now

Current values

PRESSURE HEIGHT

5250

m

++++ OZONE MIXING RATIO

45.63

ppb

All

Flight B491 16:04:04

Heading 327 deg Speed 294 knots Height 15.9kft Press 550mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 3°54.0'W Wind 12 ms-1/ 337 deg

Temp -25.9C Dewpoint -41.64C

From 15:13:54 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP
++++ DEW POINT

4856.56 m
-25.9 deg C
-41.65 deg C

All
●
○

Flight B491 16:02:45

Heading 87 deg Speed 287 knots Height 16.7kft Press 532mb

Lat 52°18.0'N Long 3°54.0'W Wind 12 ms-1/ 352 deg

Temp -27.73C Dewpoint -46.52C

From 15:13:54 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
Current value: 5102.03 m

Current value: 293.79 K

○ All
○

Flight B491 16:11:33

Heading 233 deg Speed 277 knots Height 14.7kft Press 578mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 4°0.0'W Wind 10 ms-1/ 339 deg

Temp -22.88C Dewpoint -40.37C

From 15:38:43 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
OZONE MIXING RATIO

14.72 Kft
40.02 ppb

All

Flight B491 16:10:58

Heading 342 deg Speed 278 knots Height 15.1kft Press 569mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 3°54.0'W Wind 11 ms-1/ 339 deg

Temp -24.43C Dewpoint -41.41C

From 15:38:43 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
++++ POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE

15.11 Kft
292.17 K

⊙ All
○

Flight B491 17:27:55

Heading 0 deg Speed 274 knots Height 17.7kft Press 512mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 3°54.0'W Wind 14 ms-1/ 334 deg

Temp -29.1C Dewpoint -51.79C

From 17:02:56 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
OZONE MIXING RATIO

17.71 kft
44.68 ppb

All
C

Flight B491 17:28:53

Heading 285 deg Speed 273 knots Height 17.2kft Press 521mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 3°54.0'W Wind 12 ms-1/ 327 deg

Temp -28.24C Dewpoint -50.98C

From 17:01:08 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
++++ POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE

17.25 Kft
294.93 K

All

Flight B491 17:26:58

Heading 103 deg Speed 282 knots Height 18.0kft Press 503mb

Lat 52°18.0'N Long 4°0.0'W Wind 13 ms-1/ 350 deg

Temp -29.97C Dewpoint -50.54C

From 17:02:55 to now

Current values

++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	18.1	Kft	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
++++	NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	-13.27	m s-1	<input type="checkbox"/>
++++	EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	2.22	m s-1	<input type="checkbox"/>

All

Flight B491 17:35:40

Heading 344 deg Speed 272 knots Height 14.4kft Press 583mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 3°54.0'W Wind 11 ms-1/ 321 deg

Temp -22.24C Dewpoint -40.54C

From 17:02:55 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
++++ NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT
++++ EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT

14.5
-9
7.11

Kft
m s-1
m s-1

All

Flight B491 16:36:02

Heading 285 deg Speed 308 knots Height 24.2kft Press 388mb

Lat 52°42.0'N Long 4°6.0'W Wind 44 ms-1/ 341 deg

Temp -36.97C Dewpoint -55.92C

From 15:38:43 to now

Current values

++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT
++++ POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE

24.27 Kft
309.54 K

All

